

Integrating Disaster Risk Management into Digital Health Technologies: an Indonesian Perspective

SETYA WINARNO, SRI KUSUMADEWI, ANDREJ PRÍVARA, ANETTA CAPLANOVA,
AND MKIYES HUSSEIN*

ABSTRACT

Several Indonesian major disasters have resulted in substantial health issues related to application of Digital Health Technologies (DHT) in the context of disaster risk management. The aim of this study is to explore the health sector's involvement with the Disaster Risk Management (DRM) in Indonesia. The research was conducted by examining perceptions of respondents regarding the influence of DHT on disaster risk management and ascertaining the potential role of the stakeholders. The research has found it to be an imperative for disciplines and actors in the health sector to actively engage together in both disaster risk management and DHT activities, involve multiple stakeholders with multi-target audiences to develop a sharing effort and responsibility. Regulatory changes regarding the roles, information quality and standard, interoperability of digital health platforms, and the concurrent policy implications of these changes should be implemented in all health contexts by incorporation of 'sense of place' and 'people-centred approach'.

Keywords: Digital Health Technology, Disaster Risk Management, Integration, Indonesia

JEL codes: I19, H12

1. Introduction

Indonesia is highly prone to natural disasters and is proclaimed as one of the most disastrous countries in the world. Cross sectionally, Indonesia at large encountered nearly 2000 common disasters such as storm, flood, landslide, and fires between 2019 and 2023. Moreover, there have been more than 183 events of earthquakes with high intensity; these belong to the most abominable and catastrophic natural disasters of the world (BNPB, 2023). Furthermore, apart from loss of human lives and properties, Indonesia is affected by huge financial losses in the form of health care costs every time it grapples with or in the process of recovering from disastrous natural occurrences. Furthermore, the survivors of the natural disasters are at the precarious risk of all sorts of diseases due to the shortage of health facilities and services availability. Indeed, it is evident that most of these injuries and the diseases can be averted or at least prevented (Pascapurnama et al. , 2018). Although identifying natural disasters like earthquakes is extremely tricky, there is a lot that can be done in reducing the impact of the health-related complications thereof.

Considering these threats, it will be difficult to deny the occurrence of natural disasters and its future thread to the communities in Indonesian. As a result, they have to deal with these risks within their everyday practices, as sometimes disasters can happen shortly and with no prior notice (Khan et al., 2020).

Considering the fact, the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) responded by implementing what is known as the Hyogo Framework for Action in 2005, which replaced the earlier disaster management approach of emergency response to disasters.

*Setya Winarno (corresponding author): Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Universitas Islam Indonesia. E-mail: winarno@uii.ac.id; Sri Kusumadewi: Associate Professor, Department of Informatics, Universitas Islam Indonesia. E-mail: cici@uii.ac.id; Andrej Privara: Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Faculty of National Economy, University of Economics, Bratislava, Slovakia. E-mail: andrej.privara@euba.sk; Anetta Caplanova: Professor of Economics, Department of Economics, Faculty of Economics and Finance, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia. E-mail: anetta.caplanova@euba.sk; Mkiyes Hussein: Lecturer, Department of Economics, Faculty of National Economy, University of Economics, Bratislava, Slovakia. E-mail: hussein.mkiyes@euba.sk.

This framework focuses on systematic identification and handling of the threat to health in disaster based on hazard, exposure and vulnerability (UNISDR, 2011). Moreover, over the past years, Indonesia's healthcare system has shifted from a cure oriented to a coverage that emphasis both on prevention and treatment. However, disaster health management has mainly concentrated on the post disaster response while rarely focused on management of health risks (IMH, 2021). Additionally, the growing world population further exacerbates adverse health effects of natural disasters, highlighting the need to improve disaster mitigation in Indonesia.

Moreover, different stakeholders address health related issues by adopting different approaches where they implement new practices along with new objectives (Najafi et al., 2022). While, as much as clinical factors are key determinants of public health, it is worth remembering that health is contextual, and that health status is shaped by environments, socio-cultural, policies, political and economic structures of a country (Graham and White, 2016). Thus, these elements must be integrated to address effectively health risks in relation to disasters.

Given the increase in the frequency and the degree of disaster, climate and healthcare changes, the world needs to establish resilient healthcare systems. Thus, DHT is considered as one of the solutions to healthcare crises, emergencies, and preparedness (Tomkins et al., 2023). In particular, DHT augments the availability of healthcare services, reduces deficiency, makes it less costly, and enables inter-connectivity of patients records and information. A good example can be that DHT provided health care throughout the COVID-19 pandemic with the compliance of the established public health standards and measures (ADB, 2021; Tilahun et al., 2021a). However private sectors have adopted and developed DHTs in Indonesia but, still there is no proper integration of DHTs, and updating strategies do not include DRM (IMH, 2021). Therefore, research gap exists with regarding to the implementation of DHT, stakeholder's roles, and its integration within Indonesia.

Thus, our main research question is structured as "how do the integration of the DRM, DHT, knowledge, stakeholder's role, and the Indonesian context work well? The main objective of this research is intended to establish the existing level of understanding as well as the engagement of the health sector in DRM in the context of integration at the Indonesia case. The findings of the conducted survey in this research are offering the basis for subsequent research and practical actions for integrating the DRM into the DHT. The paper is structured as introduction, literature review, methodology, results and discussion, and conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature and Background

Due to the high vulnerability of Indonesia to natural disasters, the country needs to integrate health risk factors with disaster plan and its implementation strategies, including the disease prevention, response and recovery phase (Tomkins et al., 2023). Additionally, health prevention should not be reactive measures but rather a systematic measure that encompasses planning for resilience. Further, the communities require developing a sense of place believes in handling disaster risks, and the local health authorities require improving health communication and perceiving the inhabitants' standpoint (Khan et al., 2020; Soldatovic et al., 2016). Moreover, various aspects of implementing DHT are recognized to have great potential in enhancing health care delivery, highlighted especially during the COVID-19 outbreak (ADB, 2021; Tilahun et al., 2021a). Nevertheless, it is still a developing process to apply DHT within the DRM system in Indonesia. Additionally, the government has invested hugely in the ICT and improving the health care delivery system while private sectors have created applications to provide better health services (CEDM-HA 2021; Prasadya 2020). In particular, the draft of Digital Health Transformation Strategy 2024 of Indonesia 2024 and the "SatuSehat" platform are the two initiatives to integrate the health data for improving efficient response and better DRM (IMH 2021; SatuSehat 2023). Additionally, it is believed that effective digital health

transformation necessitates systematic integrated efforts by the government, stakeholders, healthcare providers, private sector, communities, and volunteers (UNV, 2012; Wong et al., 2022). Therefore, addressing the new clinical, social, cultural, and political factors through more effective synergy and integrated approaches will further improve disaster response and health care management (Ekşi, Altay, and Gümüşsoy 2022). Additionally, it is crucial for Indonesia to link and synchronize digital health technologies with disaster health risk management across multiple sectors, to improve the health system's preparedness and performance, and patients' and providers' well-being in disaster related situations. This possible through an integrated strategy to build an efficient health care system which is able to operate, mitigate and manage disaster-related health risks. Figure 1 illustrates a conceptual multi-actor framework for DHTs.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the DHT

Source: Dar et al. (2014)

Numerous studies have explored the role of DHT in disaster scenarios, revealing gaps in research specifically concerning Indonesia's context and its integration with disaster health risk management which is depicted in figure 2. The research gap was identified in relation to a lack of health publications that directly discuss the relationship between the DHT and Indonesia as well as the connection between disaster health risk management and Indonesia. Furthermore, literature indicates that there are nine major stakeholders involved in the disaster risk management sector that include government, NGO's, donor, community, environmentalist, regional corporations, private sector, academia, and media (Fazari and Kasim, in 2019; Ogra et al., in 2021). While, in the implementation phase actors such as health sector policymakers and decision-makers, the management of affiliated hospitals, health professionals, and health volunteers play a key role in Indonesian settings (Songwathana & Timalsina, 2021; Gowing et al., 2017; Deeny & McFetridge, 2005; Espinoza et al., 2019). Moreover, use of DHT improving warning systems, providing efficient use of resources, telemedicine, health data analyzing, emergency communication, and public health awareness (Tomkins et al., 2023). But DRM practices with DHT in Indonesia require further investigation for strengthening the preparedness of the response in addressing disasters risks. Consequently, addressing these gaps

will contribute to more effective disaster mitigation strategies tailored to Indonesia's unique challenges and contexts. The map depicted in Figure 2 illustrates the atlas of terms derived from textual data that is associated with the designated keywords during the conducted literature search.¹

Figure 2. Literature Map

Source: Literature review data collected by authors

The study of the effectiveness of DHT indicates that it has been effective in the different disaster types, specifically in the developed nations. For example, the incorporation of early warning health information into the applications increases the capability of timely notification and preparedness (Hosseini et al., 2020; Kamalrathne et al., 2023). Additionally, real-time surveillance and monitoring of diseases' spread through DHT facilitates the formulation of proper response mechanisms (Xiong, Hu, and Wang, 2021; Wang, Meng, and Zhu, 2022), while tracking technologies can enhance supply chain and distribution of essential resources especially during disasters (Badawy and Radovic, 2020; Khusna et al., 2023). Moreover, there is no denial that telemedicine can be tremendously pivotal in delivering remote health where physical access to healthcare facilities is limited (Naamani et al., 2022; Gulzari and Tarakci, 2021). Moreover, the management and analysis of health data play a role, in making decisions in DRM (Munawar et al., 2022; Oktari et al., 2023). This involves studying illness trends and health risks by analyzing datasets (Kusumadewi et al., 2020; 2022a; 2022b). Additionally digital platforms help in sharing information during emergencies and facilitating effective communication among health authorities (Kordova & Hirschprung, 2023; Malik et al., 2021). Furthermore, digital health technologies contribute to educating the public about health risks using simulations and social media platforms (Samarakkody et al., 2023; Ruslanjari et al., 2023). These initiatives do not increase awareness. Also involve communities in preparing for and responding to disasters (Yazdani et al., 2022; Vera, Colbert, and Lerma, 2020). In general,

¹ Based on Figure 2, the research gap was identified in relation to a lack of health publications that directly discuss the relationship between the DHT and Indonesia as well as the connection between disaster health risk management and Indonesia.

incorporating health technologies in disaster situations improves response times and public health outcomes, underscoring their importance in reducing global disaster impacts.

3. Methodology

The primary sources of data utilized in this study is based on online surveys to efficiently reach out to a diverse population and conduct comprehensive interviews to elicit individualized responses that would provide insights into participants' subjective perceptions, encompassing their beliefs, thoughts, perspectives, viewpoints, and experiences. This approach is specifically designed to fulfil the need for triangulating data sources.

The literature review identified six emerging issues that are relevant for primary data collection and was used in the development of the questionnaire: (A1) early warning and monitoring; (A2) logistics and resource management; (A3) healthcare services during a disaster; (A4) ease of planning and decision-making; (A5) ease of emergency communications; and (A6) increasing public education and awareness. Three stakeholder groups were identified, which are directly involved in the digital health technologies (IMH 2021; UNV 2012), i.e. Policymakers, Health Professionals, and Health Volunteers affiliated with civil organizations.

The initial version of the questionnaire was used in a pilot study to enhance the clarity of the research objectives, identify the appropriate target respondents, ensure the suitability of the questions for the respondents, finetune questions and the questionnaire. This pilot study encompassed two primary tasks, specifically to check the content validity and its reliability. The measurement of content validity involved assessing the opinions of respondents regarding the extent to which the domain had been sufficiently addressed. The concept of reliability pertains to the extent to which a questionnaire demonstrates consistent performance as assessed through the examination of Cronbach's alpha coefficient that measured the internal consistency, or reliability, of a set of survey items. The pilot research study using in-depth interviews was carried out with six individuals for the content validity test, and thirty respondents were used in the reliability test.

The primary data collection was carried out using a questionnaire survey through online google form.² The questionnaires were distributed to the three groups of stakeholder representatives and focused on the Java Island, where around 60% of the Indonesian population resides and has a significant proportion of highly educated citizens (including West Java, Middle Java, and East Java). The respondents were grouped based on their gender, age, and education level. The respondent distribution employed a network comprising hospital institutions, policymaker administrations, civil organizations, and researchers. 365 respondents filled the questionnaire, 44 respondents were excluded due to inaccuracies in their reported characteristics. Thus, 321 responses were included in the analysis. The respondents reside in several cities including Jakarta, Yogyakarta, Semarang, Bandung, Jember, Kediri, Tegal, Brebes, Kebumen, Surakarta, Sleman, Kulonprogo, Cirebon, and Cianjur. Data is presented in Privara (2024).

In addition, interviews were used in which six respondents were selected to represent three distinct groups of stakeholders. The purpose of this approach was to further explore the findings obtained from the questionnaire. The interviews encompassed the subjects addressed in the questionnaire survey and provided the chance to elaborate and highlight examples and approaches, along with suggestions regarding the involvement of the three stakeholder groups in the context of integrating DRM into the DHT. This allowed to uncover areas of the integration DRM into the DHT that were not studied previously. The analysis of interview transcripts was conducted with the NVivo qualitative data analysis software. Additionally, the data was analyzed using SPSS to present a comprehensive picture of those aspects related to DRM that can be included in the DHT. Additionally, it intended to analyze the relationship

² A copy of the questionnaire is provided in the appendixes.

among three respondent's groups using Spearman Rho correlation. Further, it helped to explain the relationship between the view on each integration aspect and the respondent's characteristics, including gender, age, and education using the Crosstab Chi-Square and regression analysis.

4. Result and Discussion

The questionnaires were distributed after conducting the pilot study in order to examine the content validity test and reliability test. The respondents were selected from representatives of three stakeholders residing in Yogyakarta and its surrounding areas. The process of evaluating content validity entailed gathering the six perspectives of participants in order to determine the degree to which the subject matter had been adequately covered. The reliability test of the instrument was conducted with 30 respondents, using Cronbach's alpha coefficient that measured the internal consistency, or reliability, of a set of survey items, based on the respondents' understanding of the items in the questionnaire. With $n = 30$, $\alpha = 5\%$, and $df = 28$, the r -table is 0.3610. The reliability test results show that the r -count is 0.8302, meaning r -count $>$ r -table. Thus, it was concluded that the questionnaire is reliable. Figure 3 shows the distribution of respondents by gender, age, and education.³

Figure 3. Distribution of Respondents

Source: Survey data collected by authors

Additionally, Table 1 describes the mean, their percentages, and rank in relation to the six integration aspects of DRM into the DHT in Indonesia which are represented by three groups of respondents.⁴ The Percentage in the bottom row represent the relative importance of stakeholder roles in all integration aspects.

Table 1. Summary Statistics by Groups and Integration Aspects

Integration aspects	Policymakers		Health Professionals		Health Volunteers		Average	Rank
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank		
A1	3.54	1	3.48	2	3.40	2	3.47	2
A2	3.49	2	3.48	2	3.36	3	3.46	3
A3	3.46	4	3.42	6	3.33	6	3.41	6
A4	3.46	4	3.44	4	3.35	5	3.43	4
A5	3.49	2	3.50	1	3.45	1	3.49	1
A6	3.41	6	3.44	4	3.36	3	3.42	5

³ The questionnaire consisted of six aspects of DRM relevant for the DHT, based on the literature review. Additionally, respondents were asked to grade their agreement of the six aspects of integration of DRM into the DHT. Here, the descriptive dimension of agreement scale was converted into numerical value (a Likert scale) using the four-point bipolar agreement scale, with contrasting adjectives at each end (i.e., 4=strongly agree; 3=agree; 2=disagree; 1=strongly disagree). Hence, the respondents could be forced to declare their opinions and there was not required neutral option. Additionally, Distribution of respondents based on: (a) Stakeholder Groups, (b) Gender, (c) Age, and (d) Education.

⁴ A mean score as the average of all the responses in the data set was assigned by adding all the respondents' scores in the same group within the related aspect and then dividing it by the number of respondents. The overall mean score then was calculated in the same manner. The rank of each aspect in each group of respondents was obtained by ranking it from the highest of mean scores in the same group among the six aspects to the lowest. The overall ranking was done in the same way. If two or more aspects shared the same average/mean score, they also share the same ranking. The range of the ranks was assigned from 1 to 6. The percentage indicates the relative importance of stakeholder roles in all integration aspects.

Average	3.48	3.46	3.38	3.45
Percentage	33.71%	33.56%	32.74%	

Source: Survey data collected by authors

The survey analysis presented in Table 1 reveals overwhelming support for integrating DRM into Indonesia's Digital Health Technology (DHT), with 99.27% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing. All respondent groups had average mean scores above 3.45, with policymakers scoring the highest at 3.48 and health volunteers the lowest at 3.38. The highest-rated integration aspect was emergency communications via digital health services (mean score 3.49), while telemedicine during disasters scored lowest at 3.41 but was still rated highly by 97.82% of respondents. Overall, the strong validation of integration aspects indicates broad agreement and numerous opportunities for stakeholder engagement, aligning with Fazari and Kasim (2019). Additionally, Policymakers, Health Professionals, and Health Volunteers assign relatively high importance to their roles in all integration aspects (33.71%, 33.56%, and 32.74% respectively). Although the Policymakers perceive their role as most important, the overall responses do not yield a very extreme result. The highest perceived importance of Policymakers might correspond to their fundamental role and engagement of the government for ensuring the citizens safety as defined by Suryahadi et al. (2017). Further analysis of this result will be conducted by using Spearman 'rho' ranking correlation.

In the Policymaker group, five out of six aspects exhibit scores that are higher than the average score of 3.45. The score below 3.45 is only for A6 (Digital health services have an impact on enhancing public knowledge and awareness). Conversely, in the Health Volunteer group, five out of six aspects have scores below the average score of 3.45 and the only A5 aspect receives more than the average score. But the majority of participants still considered these five aspects to be highly significant, despite the fact that most of them assigned only a score of 3 (agree). Additionally, respondents had the most aligned view on the aspect A5 (Digital health services help and facilitate emergency communication, especially during disasters) with the average mean score of 3.49. This finding might be influenced by the fact that the emergency response during disaster have been put as the higher priority rather than a prevention of disaster risk (Okońska et al., (2020). Moreover, emergency response activities might be often used by people and politicians to gain kudos from being associated with humanitarian responses. According to the ranks in Table 1, the most interesting result comes from the response to A5 (Digital health services help and facilitate emergency communication, especially during disasters). Two groups of respondents out of three ranked A5 as the first one. Only Policymakers indicated the first rank to be A1. Similarly, two groups of respondents ranked A3 last and, overall, A3 ranked as the last one. Between the first and last, the remainder of ranks are scattered evenly without evidence of a pattern. Further, A4 that is related to data management based on a health people-centered approach, and disaster risk zones for systematic planning represents a unique aspect for the integration DRM into the DHT. According to Senbekov et al. (2020), the systematic intervention of both health people-centered approach and disaster risk zones poses a new challenge in Indonesia, given the country's cultural and societal diversities in these areas.

Further detailed analysis of the data based on gender, age, and educational background is presented in the Appendixes Tables 1-3.⁵ Table 1 of the appendixes indicates that female respondents exhibit greater scores in the Policymakers and Health Volunteers groups, whereas the Health Professionals group does not. Overall, this suggests that women play a more significant role than men in the process of this integration. The importance of women in disaster response has been highlighted by Ekşi et al. (2022) that points out that female volunteers have

⁵ Specifically, the data lacks information on the Postgraduate academic background for just the Health Volunteer respondent group as described in Table 3 of the appendix. While Tables 1, 2, and 3 display the average scores and their rankings according to gender, age, and education respectively.

a crucial role in increasing available social resilience during disasters due to their unique attributes such as motherhood, which is socio-culturally regarded as a beneficial quality and an advantage for the common good of a society. Table 2 of the appendixes illustrates that all respondents who are considered mature in terms of age, express highest agreement with the integration aspects. The findings are related to the study conducted by Carpenter and Yoon (2011), which mentions that decision-making abilities generally undergo a progressive transformation as individuals grow older. Elderly individuals exhibit enhanced capacity for methodical information processing under specific circumstances. The propensity to make sound decisions reaches its highest point around the age of 53 and then decreases as individuals enter older stages of adulthood. Additionally, according to the academic background, Table 3 of the appendixes demonstrates that the Group of Health Professionals exhibits a positive correlation between the mean score and higher degrees of education. Similarly, Kim et al. (2018) emphasize that education can strengthen the rationality of decision-makers. Education enhances individuals' capacity to make informed and effective decisions that significantly impact their life. Nevertheless, there is no discernible correlation between the rising educational attainment of Policymakers and Health Volunteers and an increase in the average score. As a results, the importance of a higher level of education for Health Professionals is essential for properly addressing the integration concerns, which is a new challenge.

The above findings (Table 1) confirm that the percentage of the relative importance of the three stakeholder roles in terms of integration aspects do not exhibit extreme results. Because Policymakers, Health Professionals, Health Volunteers have different duties and responsibilities, thus it is relevant to evaluate whether there is a correlation between the two groups of respondents regarding six integration aspects or not. Thus, Table 2 presents a statistical significance test of the difference between the proportions of respondent opinions. Further, according to the ordinal number employed in the scoring value, the Spearman 'rho' correlation is employed to provide an indication of the relationship among the three groups of respondents.

Table 2. The Spearman's rho Correlations Matrix

Groups	(1)	(2)	(3)
(1) Policymakers	1.000	0.794*	0.612
(2) Health Professionals	0.794*	1.000	0.899**
(3) Health Volunteers	0.612	0.899***	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Survey data, and SPSS analysis by authors

Based on the earlier analysis, the positive correlation indicates that a high ranking in one variable corresponds to a high ranking in the other. Therefore, one tail test of significance was chosen for this correlation in order to support a positive direction.⁶ The calculation describes an overall disagreement between all groups toward 'integration aspects'. This indicates that the high ranking given by one group of respondents to the 'integrations aspects' does not correspond to high ranking given by the other group to the same aspects, and vice versa. In summary, there is no significant agreement from every group of respondents concerning the rank of the six integration aspects. Broadly speaking, all respondents are relatively heterogenous and do not share the same characteristics with regard to ranking. Although responder groups may perceive the 'integration aspects' differently, they have certain duties in managing the disaster risks, as explained by Ogra et al. (2021). Therefore, it is crucial for the three parties to cooperate together in the process and prioritize the integration of DRM

⁶ The result provides the boundaries of a confidence interval that these research data is able to produce 99% confidence limits or the probability of the result due to chance is less than one percent ($P < 0.01$). Concerning the tail test of significance and $P < 0.01$, the *rho* critical value (r_c) for the Spearman '*rho*' correlation is $r_c = 0.943$ adopted from the Spearman '*rho*' standard table. The results shows that there are three correlation values: $rho_1 = 0.794$; $rho_2 = 0.612$; $rho_3 = 0.899$ and all the *rhos*' is below *rho critical values* ($< r_c = 0.943$): concluding that all groups of respondents have no significant correlation, or all groups of respondents perceive the 'integration aspects' differently.

into DHT. This will significantly contribute to minimizing the disparity and facilitate the integration in the correct direction.

Cross-tabulation analysis helps to draw correlations between two variables (gender, age, or education and the agreement level of the six integration aspects within this study). Table 3 shows the cross-tabulation results for this examination. If the approximate significance-value is less than or equal to the alpha-value of 0.05, then the two variables are correlated. ⁷ Based on Table 3, it can be concluded that gender has no significant correlation to the level of agreement of the integration aspects, while age and education have a significant correlation.

Table 3. Result of Cross-tabulation Analysis

Tests	Gender	Age	Education
Pearson's R (Interval by Interval)	0.051 ^c (0.056) ^a	0.181*** ^c (0.055) ^a	0.173*** ^c (0.058) ^a
Spearman Correlation (Ordinal by Ordinal)	0.056 ^c (0.056) ^a	0.177*** ^c (0.055) ^a	0.175*** ^c (0.057) ^a
N of Valid Cases	321	321	321

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Survey data, and SPSS analysis by authors

To determine the magnitude of the significant value between variables, Table 4 outlines the regression analysis to enhance the robustness of the findings. The regression analysis uncovered substantial correlations between six integration aspects and the respondent's score, taking into account age and education. However, the gender does not have a significant impact. The results are consistent with the findings of cross-tabulation analysis presented in Table 6. This highlights a positive relationship between the age of the respondents and their agreement with the implementation of six integration aspects. A positive link is also observed at the higher education level of the respondents in the same context. Additionally, the regression coefficient for respondents based on age is greater than the regression coefficient for respondents based on education for variables A1, A2, A3, and A4. Indeed, there is a challenge in determining the extent to which age and education are significantly associated with the level of agreement on the integration aspects.

Table 4. Regression Result

VARIABLES	(1) A1	(2) A2	(3) A3	(4) A4	(4) A5	(4) A6
Gender	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Age	1.614***	1.647	1.915***	1.519**	1.518**	1.356*
Education	1.361**	1.481***	1.258**	1.619***	1.454***	1.382**
Observations	321	321	321	321	321	321

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Survey data, and SPSS analysis by authors

In addition, our finding indicates that DHT integration into DRM brings about challenges and opportunities, a summary of which is attached in Table 4 of the Appendixes. It indicates that it is critical to have a peculiar method that blends “sense of place” with a “people-centric” approach (Senbekov et al., 2020). Furthermore, community involvement as well as instruction are vital for local disaster readiness (UNISDR, 2011). Particularly in Indonesia

⁷ Pearson's R measures the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables, assuming a normal distribution and evaluating significance without assuming the null hypothesis. It uses asymptotic standard errors to estimate the precision of the correlation coefficient. Spearman's correlation, a non-parametric measure, evaluates monotonic relationships between variables based on their ranks, also using asymptotic standard errors and normal approximation to assess significance. The value in brackets represents the Asymptotic Standard Error, which is not assuming the null hypothesis, and the first number represents the value of the test with their significance annotation. Further, the star represents the approximate significance level. While “a” denotes Not assuming the null hypothesis, “b” denotes using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis, and “c” denotes Based on normal approximation.

which is prone to disasters it is important to understand the specific disaster areas and their health consequences (BNPB, 2023). Additionally, the aspect of “place” cultivates trust and motivation within communities thereby creating a sustainable environment (Khan et al., 2020). Also, higher educational achievements result in systematic thinking on DRM. It is cost effective to take a multi-disciplinary approach towards preventive allocation of resources for health risks (BNPB, 2023). Policy implications suggest that strong political commitment, financial resources and efficient communication systems are necessary (Senbekov et al., 2020). In addition, participation by the private sector in digital health platforms presents opportunities for integrating DRM that enhance community resilience (Khan et al., 2020).

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The occurrence of natural disasters in Indonesia has led to the emerging need for the implementation of both comprehensive disaster health risk management and DHT to address healthcare crises, preparedness, and response. In fact, it is evident in Indonesia that the integration of DRM into DHT is not currently being achieved. In relation to integration, this study has found that the most prominent challenging factors are the incorporation of a ‘sense of place’ and ‘people-centered’ approach within all integration aspects. The integration process will yield better outcomes when undertaken by parties and personnel with higher educational achievement, as they are capable of delivering systematic and comprehensive thinking.

It is imperative for the disciplines and actors in the health sectors to actively and integratively engage in both DRM and DHT activities in Indonesia. As this integration is a novel approach in DHT, involvement of multidisciplinary stakeholders should embrace multi-target audiences to develop a sharing effort and responsibility in DRM in daily life. This will be required to pre-empt any likely regulatory changes regarding the roles, information quality and standard, and interoperability of digital health platforms and the concurrent policy implications of these changes on all health circumstances. This greater DHT integration needs deeper consideration on the development of digital health platform, testing, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation processes. The ‘SatuSehat’ platform, created by the Indonesian Ministry of Health, can serve as the primary platform for integrating DRM into DHT. Therefore, government roles as a proactive backbone and inclusion of existing social bonds and/or indigenous approach will be key to the integration.

If an integration of DRM into DHT in Indonesia is to be achieved, several aspects need to become mainstreamed into the development of digital health platform, testing, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation processes. Based on the literature, questionnaire survey, and in-depth interviews, this could be achieved through constructive measures. One such measures is the involvement of local actors as a prominent factor to incorporate a ‘sense of place’ and ‘people-centered’ approach within all integration aspects. Additionally, improve educational background of Health Professionals as a group responsible for providing suggestions for the development of the health care system, especially related to the implementation of telemedicine and knowledge support in the decision-making. This group also acts as a health care actor both through digital media, including those developed by hospitals, and digital platforms developed by the private sector. Furthermore, policymakers as a group responsible for policy management must provide a mandate or obligation to all stakeholders to play an active role in the integration of DRM into DHT. It is necessary to anticipate potential regulatory changes related to the functions, content, and interoperability of digital health platforms, as well as the policy implications of these changes in all health contexts. Thus, to accelerate and maintain the consistency in this integration, a strong commitment from all parties is needed. The government, academic, and private institutions need to invest in training, education, research, and collaboration with national and regional authorities to establish a robust monitoring and evaluation system to support continuous improvement efforts.

Acknowledgment

The authors express their gratitude to the management of Universitas Islam Indonesia for providing the essential research infrastructure for this study. The research underlying this paper was co-funded by Project “Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia (ODDEA)”, No. 101086381, European Commission HORIZON-MSCA-SE Scheme. The authors express their sincere appreciation to the administration of JIH Hospital, Jember Hospital, Tegal Hospital, and Kebumen Hospital, as well as several governmental institutions and civil organizations across Java island, for their important assistance in facilitating this research.

References

- ADB. 2021. *Digital Health Implementation Guide for The Pasific*. Metro Manila, Philippines: Asian Development Bank.
- Badawy, Sherif M, and Ana Radovic. 2020. “Digital Approaches to Remote Pediatric Health Care Delivery During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Existing Evidence and a Call for Further Research.” *JMIR Pediatrics and Parenting* 3 (1): e20049.
- BNPB. 2023. “Badan Nasional Penanggulangan Bencana: Kasus Kejadian Bencana Alam Di Indonesia Tahun 2019-2023.” <https://Dibi.Bnpb.Go.Id/>. 2023.
- Callagy, Patrice, Shashank Ravi, Saud Khan, Maame Yaa A.B. Yiadom, Hannah McClellan, Samuel Snell, Thomas W. Major, and Maria Yefimova. 2021. “Operationalizing a Pandemic-Ready, Telemedicine-Enabled Drive-Through and Walk-In Coronavirus Disease Garage Care System as an Alternative Care Area: A Novel Approach in Pandemic Management.” *Journal of Emergency Nursing* 47 (5): 721–32.
- Carpenter, Stephanie M., and Carolyn Yoon. 2011. “Aging and Consumer Decision Making.” *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1235 (1).
- CEDM-HA. 2021. Center for Excellence in Disaster Management and Humanitarian Assistance: Indonesia Disaster Management Reference Handbook. Hickam, Hawaii.
- Dar, Osman, Emmeline J. Buckley, Sakib Rokadiya, Qudsia Huda, and Jonathan Abrahams. 2014. “Integrating Health Into Disaster Risk Reduction Strategies: Key Considerations for Success.” *American Journal of Public Health* 104 (10): 1811–16.
- Deeny, Pat, and Brian McFetridge. 2005. “The Impact of Disaster on Culture, Self, and Identity: Increased Awareness by Health Care Professionals Is Needed.” *Nursing Clinics of North America* 40 (3): 431–40.
- Ekşi, Ali, Sinem Utanır Altay, and Süreyya Gümüşsoy. 2022. “The Role of Female Volunteers in Disaster Response Organisations: A Qualitative Research.” *Work* 73 (4): 1421–31.
- Espinoza, Adriana E., Paulina Osorio Parraguez, and Elvis Posada Quiroga. 2019. “Preventing Mental Health Risks in Volunteers in Disaster Contexts: The Case of the Villarrica Volcano Eruption, Chile.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 34 (March): 154–64.
- Fazari, S.A.L, and Narimah Kasim. 2019. “Role of Stakeholders in Mitigating Disaster Prevalence: Theoretical Perspective.” *MATEC Web of Conferences* 266 (February): 03008.
- Gowing, Jeremy R., Kim N. Walker, Shandell L. Elmer, and Elizabeth A. Cummings. 2017. “Disaster Preparedness among Health Professionals and Support Staff: What Is Effective? An Integrative Literature Review.” *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 32 (3): 321–28.
- Graham, H., and P.C.L. White. 2016. “Social Determinants and Lifestyles: Integrating Environmental and Public Health Perspectives.” *Public Health* 141 (December): 270–78.
- Gulzari, Adeela, and Hakan Tarakci. 2021. “A Healthcare Location-Allocation Model with an Application of Telemedicine for an Earthquake Response Phase.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 55 (March): 102100.

- Hosseini, Seyed Hossein, Hamid Reza Khankeh, Mehrdad Farrokhi, Mohammad Ali Hosseini, Pirhossein Koolivand, and Mohammad Raeiszadeh. 2020. "Early Warning System-Related Challenges in Health Sector: A Qualitative Content Analysis Study in Iran." *J Educ Health Promot* 38 (9).
- IMH. 2021. "Indonesian Ministry of Health: Blue Print of Digital Health Transformation Strategy 2024." Jakarta.
- Kamalrathne, Thushara, Dilanthi Amaratunga, Richard Haigh, and Lahiru Kodituwakku. 2023. "Need for Effective Detection and Early Warnings for Epidemic and Pandemic Preparedness Planning in the Context of Multi-Hazards: Lessons from the COVID-19 Pandemic." *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 92 (June): 103724.
- Khan, Garee, Javed Akhter Qureshi, Anwar Khan, Attaullah Shah, Sajid Ali, Iram Bano, and Muhammad Alam. 2020. "The Role of Sense of Place, Risk Perception, and Level of Disaster Preparedness in Disaster Vulnerable Mountainous Areas of Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 27 (35): 44342–54.
- Khusna, Nur Isroatul, Sumarmi, Syamsul Bachri, I Komang Astina, Singgih Susilo, and Idris. 2023. "Social Resilience and Disaster Resilience: A Strategy in Disaster Management Efforts Based on Big Data Analysis in Indonesian's Twitter Users." *Heliyon* 9 (9): e19669.
- Kim, Hyuncheol Bryant, Syngjoo Choi, Booyuel Kim, and Cristian Pop-Eleches. 2018. "The Role of Education Interventions in Improving Economic Rationality." *Science* 362 (October): 83–86.
- Kordova, Sigal, and Ron S. Hirschprung. 2023. "Effectiveness of the Forced Usage of Alternative Digital Platforms during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Project Communication Management." *Heliyon*, November, e21812.
- Kusumadewi, Sri, Linda Rosita, and Elyza Gustri Wahyuni. 2020. *Model of Clinical Decision Support System for Metabolic Syndrome*. 1st ed. Yogyakarta: UII Press.
- . 2022a. "Development of a Modified Certainty Factor Model for Prediction of Metabolic Syndrome." *International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control (IJICIC)* 18 (5): 1463–14775.
- . 2022b. "Selection of Aggregation Function in Fuzzy Inference System for Metabolic Syndrome." *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology* 12 (5): 2140.
- Malik, Aqdas, M. Laeeq Khan, and Anabel Quan Haase. 2021. "Public Health Agencies Outreach through Instagram during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication Perspective." *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 61 (July): 102346.
- Munawar, Hafiz Suliman, Mohammad Mojtahedi, Ahmed W.A. Hammad, Abbas Kouzani, and M.A. Parvez Mahmud. 2022. "Disruptive Technologies as a Solution for Disaster Risk Management: A Review." *Science of The Total Environment* 806 (February): 151351.
- Naamani, Kareem E., Rawad Abbas, Sarah Mukhtar, Omar El Fadel, Anish Sathe, Adina S. Kazan, Rayan El Hajjar, et al. 2022. "Telemedicine during and Post-COVID 19: The Insights of Neurosurgery Patients and Physicians." *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience* 99 (May): 204–11.
- Najafi, Sara, Arash Akahavan Rezayat, Seyyedeh Faezeh Beyzaei, Zahra Shahriari, Mahdieh Taheri Tabar, Mohammad Ghasemi Nour, Reza Mosaed, Majid Khadem Rezaiyan, and Ramin Hamidi Farahani. 2022. "Incidence of Infectious Diseases after Earthquakes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *Public Health* 202 (January): 131–38.
- Ogra, A., A. Donovan, G. Adamson, K.R. Viswanathan, and M. Budimir. 2021. "Exploring the Gap between Policy and Action in Disaster Risk Reduction: A Case Study from India." *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 63 (September): 102428.
- Oktari, Rina Suryani, Bokiraiya Latuamury, Rinaldi Idroes, Hizir Sofyan, and Khairul Munadi. 2023. "Knowledge Management Strategy for Managing Disaster and the COVID-19

- Pandemic in Indonesia: SWOT Analysis Based on the Analytic Network Process.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 85 (February): 103503.
- Pascapurnama, Dyshelly Nurkartika, Aya Murakami, Haorile Chagan Yasutan, Toshio Hattori, Hiroyuki Sasaki, and Shinichi Egawa. 2018. “Integrated Health Education in Disaster Risk Reduction: Lesson Learned from Disease Outbreak Following Natural Disasters in Indonesia.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 29 (August): 94–102.
- Prasidya, Yunindita. 2020. “Major Indonesian Hospitals Go Digital to Tap into Growing Telemedicine Market .” <https://www.thejakartapost.com/news/2020/05/20/major-indonesian-hospitals-go-digital-to-tap-into-growing-telemedicine-market.html>. May 20, 2020.
- Prívarva A. (2024). Survey and secondary data on digitization [online]. *Zenodo*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13756424
- Ruslanjari, Dina, Elok Wuri Safitri, Fathin Aulia Rahman, and Cahyadi Ramadhan. 2023. “ICT for Public Awareness Culture on Hydrometeorological Disaster.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 92 (June): 103690.
- Samarakkody, Aravindi, Anuradha C. Senanayake, Chamindi Malalgoda, Dilanthi Amaratunga, Richard Haigh, Champika Liyanage, Mo Hamza, Artūras Kaklauskas, and Rajib Shaw. 2023. “Inclusivity in Online and Distance Disaster Education: A Review of Educators’ Views.” *Progress in Disaster Science* 20 (December): 100298.
- SatuSehat. 2023. “Satu Platform Satu Standar Menuju Indonesia Sehat.” <https://satusehat.kemkes.go.id/platform>. 2023.
- Senbekov, Maksut, Timur Saliev, Zhanar Bukeyeva, Aigul Almabayeva, Marina Zhanaliyeva, Nazym Aitenova, Yerzhan Toishibekov, and Ildar Fakhradiyev. 2020. “The Recent Progress and Applications of Digital Technologies in Healthcare: A Review.” *International Journal of Telemedicine and Applications* 2020 (December): 1–18.
- Soldatovic, Ivan, Rade Vukovic, Djordje Culafic, Milan Gajic, and Vesna Dimitrijevic Sreckovic. 2016. “SiMS Score: Simple Method for Quantifying Metabolic Syndrome.” *PloS One* 11 (1).
- Songwathana, Praneed, and Rekha Timalisina. 2021. “Disaster Preparedness among Nurses of Developing Countries: An Integrative Review.” *International Emergency Nursing* 55 (March): 100955.
- Tilahun, Binyam, Kassahun Dessie Gashu, Zeleke Abebaw Mekonnen, Berhanu Fikadie Endehabtu, and Dessie Abebaw Angaw. 2021a. “Mapping the Role of Digital Health Technologies in Prevention and Control of COVID-19 Pandemic: Review of the Literature.” *Yearbook of Medical Informatics* 30 (01): 026–037.
- . 2021b. “Mapping the Role of Digital Health Technologies in the Case Detection, Management, and Treatment Outcomes of Neglected Tropical Diseases: A Scoping Review.” *Tropical Medicine and Health* 49 (1): 17.
- Tomkins, Zerina Lokmic, Dinesh Bhandari, Chris Bain, Ann Borda, Timothy Charles Kariotis, and David Reser. 2023. “Lessons Learned from Natural Disasters around Digital Health Technologies and Delivering Quality Healthcare.” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20 (5): 4542.
- UNISDR. 2011. “The United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction: HYOGO FRAMEWORK FOR ACTION 2005-2015 (Building the Resilience of Nations and Communities to Disasters) MID-TERM REVIEW 2010-2011.”
- UNV. 2012. “The United Nations Volunteers: Volunteerism and Disasters.” Phoenix Design Aid, Denmark.
- Vera, A Verner Venegas, Gates B Colbert, and Edgar V Lerma. 2020. “Positive and Negative Impact of Social Media in the COVID-19 Era.” *Reviews in Cardiovascular Medicine* 21 (4): 561.
- Wang, Hao, Xianhai Meng, and Xingyu Zhu. 2022. “Improving Knowledge Capture and Retrieval

in the BIM Environment: Combining Case-Based Reasoning and Natural Language Processing.” *Automation in Construction* 139 (July): 104317.

Wong, Brian Li Han, Laura Maaß, Alice Vodden, Robin van Kessel, Sebastiano Sorbello, Stefan Buttigieg, and Anna Odone. 2022. “The Dawn of Digital Public Health in Europe: Implications for Public Health Policy and Practice.” *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* 14 (March): 100316.

Xiong, Li, Peiyang Hu, and Houcai Wang. 2021. “Establishment of Epidemic Early Warning Index System and Optimization of Infectious Disease Model: Analysis on Monitoring Data of Public Health Emergencies.” *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* 65 (November): 102547.

Yazdani, Nur A, Muhammad Dewan, Tanvir Abir, Yang Qing, Jamee Ahmad, Abdullah Al Mamun, Noor Raihani Zainol, Kaniz Kakon, Kingsley Emwinyore Agho, and Shasha Wang. 2022. “Social Media Addiction and Emotions during the Disaster Recovery Period—The Moderating Role of Post-COVID Timing.” *PLOS ONE* 17 (10): e0274898.

Appendixes

Table 1. Mean Scores and Rankings Categorized by Gender

Integration aspect	Policymakers				Health Professionals				Health Volunteers			
	Male	Rank	Female	Rank	Male	Rank	Female	Rank	Male	Rank	Female	Rank
A1	3.47	1	3.58	2	3.52	2	3.47	2	3.28	4	3.63	1
A2	3.29	4	3.63	1	3.52	2	3.46	3	3.25	5	3.58	2
A3	3.29	4	3.58	2	3.45	6	3.41	6	3.22	6	3.53	4
A4	3.35	3	3.54	4	3.52	2	3.42	5	3.31	3	3.42	5
A5	3.47	1	3.50	5	3.55	1	3.48	1	3.39	1	3.58	2
A6	3.29	4	3.50	5	3.47	5	3.42	4	3.33	2	3.42	5
Average	3.36		3.56		3.51		3.44		3.30		3.53	

Source: Survey data collected by authors

Table 2. Mean Scores and Rankings Categorized by Age

#Integration aspect	Policymakers						Health Professionals						Health Volunteers					
	Y*	Rank	M**	Rank	O***	Rank	Y*	Rank	M**	Rank	O***	Rank	Y*	Rank	M**	Rank	O***	Rank
A1	3.33	1	3.67	1	3.80	1	3.42	2	3.58	2	3.58	3	3.39	2	3.38	2	3.50	1
A2	3.28	2	3.67	1	3.60	3	3.39	3	3.63	1	3.50	5	3.39	2	3.29	5	3.50	1
A3	3.22	5	3.67	1	3.60	3	3.33	6	3.55	5	3.67	2	3.31	6	3.29	5	3.50	1
A4	3.28	2	3.61	4	3.60	3	3.36	5	3.56	4	3.58	3	3.39	2	3.33	3	3.25	6
A5	3.28	2	3.61	4	3.80	1	3.44	1	3.58	2	3.75	1	3.50	1	3.43	1	3.38	4
A6	3.22	5	3.56	6	3.60	3	3.39	3	3.51	6	3.50	5	3.39	2	3.33	3	3.38	4
Average	3.27		3.63		3.67		3.39		3.57		3.60		3.40		3.34		3.42	

* Y = Young age (<35s) mean score

** M = Middle age (36s-50s) mean score

*** O = Old age (>51s) mean score

Source: Survey data collected by authors

Table 3. Mean Scores and Rankings Categorized by Education

Integration aspect	Policymakers						Health Professionals						Health Volunteers									
	S*	R	D**	R	U***	R	P****	R	S*	R	D**	R	U***	R	P****	R	S*	R	D**	R	U***	R
A1	3.55	1	3.17	6	3.67	1	3.50	2	3.50	1	3.42	2	3.50	2	3.63	5	3.29	2	3.60	1	3.46	2
A2	3.36	4	3.50	1	3.61	2	3.33	5	3.33	3	3.40	3	3.50	2	3.71	1	3.29	2	3.60	1	3.38	5
A3	3.45	2	3.33	2	3.50	4	3.50	2	3.50	1	3.37	5	3.41	6	3.67	2	3.29	2	3.40	3	3.35	6
A4	3.36	4	3.33	2	3.56	3	3.50	2	3.33	3	3.37	5	3.47	4	3.67	2	3.21	6	3.40	3	3.46	2
A5	3.45	2	3.33	2	3.50	4	3.67	1	3.33	3	3.44	1	3.54	1	3.63	5	3.33	1	3.40	3	3.58	1
A6	3.36	4	3.33	2	3.50	4	3.33	5	3.33	3	3.39	4	3.43	5	3.67	2	3.29	2	3.40	3	3.42	4
Average	3.42		3.33		3.56		3.47		3.39		3.40		3.48		3.66		3.28		3.47		3.44	

* S = Senior high school's mean score

** D = Diploma's mean score

*** U = Undergraduate's mean score

**** P = Postgraduate's mean score

Source: Survey data collected by authors

Table 4. Summary of Comments of Stakeholders on Selected Aspects of the Integration

Emerging issues	Related aspects of integration	Related comments provided
Challenge: intervention of 'sense of place' and 'people-centred' approach	A1: early warning and monitoring A4: ease of planning and decision making A5: ease of emergency communications A6: increasing public education and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local people preparedness for disasters Individual health data at the sub-village as a basis for mitigating disaster Existing local initiatives for community disaster awareness
Challenge: the importance of higher education	A3: healthcare services during a disaster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher educational achievement for delivering systematic and thorough thinking The maturity of thought and broad experiences
Opportunity: multidiscipline decision making	A2: logistics and resource management A4: ease of planning and decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborations with several sectors for sharing effort and responsibility
Policy implication: strong political commitment to disaster management	A4: ease of planning and decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A high level of devotion to execution An incident command system (ICS) model for managing large-scale catastrophes Enforcement authoritatively the commercial sector

Source: Survey data collected and analysed by authors

Table 5. Questionnaire

No	Aspects	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1	Digital health services have an impact on monitoring and early warning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital health can help in monitoring and early warning of infectious diseases or public health events that could develop into disasters. Digital monitoring systems can provide real-time data on the spread of disease, enabling rapid response and better coordination. 				
2	Digital health services affect logistics and resource				

No	Aspects	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
	management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital technology can be used to efficiently manage logistics and health resources during disasters. Integrated information systems can assist in monitoring and managing drug supplies, medical equipment, and health personnel. 				
3	Telemedicine helps healthcare services, especially during disasters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital health allows health service providers to provide services remotely, especially when physical access to health facilities is disrupted due to disasters. Telemedicine can help support patients who need care without having to move from a safe location. 				
4	Management and data analysis of digital health services help management in planning and decision-making <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis can be used to understand disease patterns, local disaster risk zones, predict risk, and develop more effective disaster risk management strategies. Data collected from various sources, including digital health, can help in better planning and decision making. 				
5	Digital health services help and facilitate emergency communications, especially during disasters <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital health supports effective emergency communications between health authorities, rescue workers and the public. Fast and accurate notifications via digital platforms can help in evacuation and reduce the impact of disasters. 				
6	Digital health services have an impact on increasing public education and awareness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital health can be used to increase public education and awareness about disaster-related health risks. Social media and online platforms can be effective tools for disseminating information and providing guidance to the public 				